

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It is a great pleasure to introduce the fifth and last regular issues of 2019. With another year of great interest indicated by downloads and reads as well as good impact numbers, we are looking very positive in the year 2020. Beginning with the first issue in 2020 we will now apply our new open content strategy to provide even more value for authors, readers and the wider research community. All of these achievements would not be possible without the generous support by the members of our consortium, our active and dedicated editorial board, the J.UCS team and most importantly the contributions by the authors. I would therefore like to thank all of you and look forward to further collaborations in the new year. I would also like to further extend our editorial board: if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board. We are also interested in high quality proposals of special issues covering emerging topics and new trends. If you are interested, send your proposal to me at c.guetl@tugraz.at.

In this regular issue, I am very happy to introduce 5 accepted papers from 8 different countries.

George-Petru Ciordas-Hertel, Jan Schneider, Stefaan Ternier and Hendrik Drachslar from Germany report on their structured literature review and propose an approach towards a trusted and interoperable learning analytics infrastructure.

In a collaborative research between Spain and Mexico, Pedro G. Espejo, Eva Gibaja, Víctor H. Menéndez, Alfredo Zapata and Cristóbal Romero propose an improved approach towards automatically learning object categorization by taking into consideration information of learning object usage and considering multiple categories by apply a multi-label learning approach.

Andreas Hinderks, Dominique Winter, Martin Schrepp and Jörg Thomaschewski elaborate in their collaborative research between Spain and Germany the analysis and applicability of user experience and usability questionnaires.

Further, in a collaborative work between Spain and Italy, J. David Paton-Romero, Maria Teresa Baldassarre, Moisés Rodríguez and Mario Piattini develop and assess a governance and management framework for green IT that may guide to gradually implement, evaluate, and improve all those aspects and characteristics of governance and management that constitutes the basis of the processes, practices, and activities of Green IT.

Estêvão B. Saleme, Celso A. S. Santos, Ricardo A. Falbo, Gheorghita Ghinea and Frederic Andres propose in their collaborative research between Brazil, Uk and Japan to establish a common conceptualization about mulsemmedia systems and to support

the design process through a domain reference ontology named MulseOnto which also has been verified and validated.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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